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Economic Viability of Aquaponics Across Global Climate Zones: A Meta-Analytical Assessment

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ABSTRACT

Aquaponic systems are emerging as sustainable agricultural solutions that conserve water and recycle waste, enabling food cultivation in urban, rural, and arid regions. They are increasingly advocated across diverse contexts, yet adoption remains limited due to concerns about economic viability stemming from huge capital investment and low profitability. In this study, we employed a metadata analysis to assess the influence of climate zones and system configurations on the profitability of soilless systems. Our findings informed the development of a data-based support tool—APECO—presented as a prototype that uses compiled metadata. Productivity in tropical climates (Aw and Am) was associated with lower energy and labor costs, which corresponded with comparatively better outcomes than temperate regions in terms of breakeven price, net return, and payback periods. However, these patterns should be interpreted with caution due to dataset imbalance, as approximately one-third of studies were conducted in the Aw climate zone, while data from other zones were sparse. Profitability also appeared to vary between configurations, but the observed divergence between coupled (revenue-linked) and decoupled (cost-linked) aquaponics should be regarded as preliminary, given that only 9% of the dataset represented decoupled systems. Plant revenue and fish yield were most strongly associated with net returns across climates, suggesting that context-specific productivity gains may play an essential role in shaping profitability. We introduced APECO as a proof-of-concept calculator designed to integrate system-specific metadata with user inputs; however, as it has not yet been validated with real-world data, its use should be regarded as illustrative, pending empirical validation.

1 | Introduction

The growing human population has continued to intensify food production across the globe. This intensification has substantially increased our ecological footprint. To sustain our current ecological demand, we would require a 1.7 Earth—an expectation that is practically impossible [1, 2]. Conventional agricultural production, which employs soil as the growing medium and occupies substantial land space, is exacerbating the impact of population growth through high irrigation water

consumption and increased use of inorganic fertilizers while limiting production to areas with fertile soils.

Soilless production methods such as bioponics, in the last decade, have emerged as sustainable production systems for modern agriculture that are adoptable in urban regions where arable lands are scarce and in arid regions [3]. Conventional aquaponics (an example of bioponics) integrates aquaculture with hydroponics, using waste from fish culture to cultivate plants in a soilless medium [4, 5]. The metabolites in the

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wastewater and suspended solids from the fish-rearing unit are broken down into absorbable nutrients that are taken up by plants for growth. This integration enables up to a 90% reduction in water use and supports food production in a limited space [6]. On the other hand, standalone hydroponics, unlike aquaponics, which uses waste from aquaculture, relies on commercial inorganic fertilizers as the source of plant nutrients [7]. Despite the growth and potential of these systems in sustainable agriculture, the food production systems still face several inherent challenges, reducing their commercial scalability and adoption.

Studies have suggested that the low adoption and commercialization of aquaponics in European regions and Australia are due to policies that classify products from these systems as nonorganic, limiting their premium market values [8, 9]. Other studies have established that high production costs and substantial initial capital investment deter potential farmers from investing in the industry [9]. There are varied and inconclusive results regarding the profitability of soilless food production methods across various regions. In studies involving the economic analysis of aquaponics in Germany, Baganz et al. [10] and Pasch and Palm [11] reported the profitability of the food production systems at large production scales. However, they recorded economic losses at smaller scales, with labor cost being the highest (44.7%) share of the total operational cost in Baganz et al. [10]. Studies such as Ascuito et al. [12], Chaves et al. [13], Goada et al. [14], Folorunso et al. [15], Rakocy et al. [16], and Souza et al. [17] have investigated the economic profitability of soilless systems in Italy, Portugal, Egypt, Nigeria, the United States, and Brazil, respectively, revealing that the economic viability of aquaponics and hydroponics is strongly influenced by scale, resource optimization, and local market dynamics.

Understanding the trends across various biological system types, economic conditions, and climatic influences may initiate an economic optimization of the systems and subsequent profitability at various production scales. For example, local climates play primary roles in the number of production cycles and the energy cost in soilless systems, among other factors [15]. Greenfeld et al. [9] evaluated the economic feasibility of aquaponics and factors limiting the adoption of the food production systems. The authors reviewed existing case-based articles, focusing on operational cost, labor cost, and policy barriers as key challenges facing the profitability and commercialization of aquaponics. Although this study emphasized aquaponics' sustainability potential, the lack of empirical economic evaluation across the system types and climatic regions limits the proper understanding of the specificity and magnitude of the factors influencing profitability. For example, coupled aquaponics, which simultaneously co-cultivates fish and plants in a single-loop system and requires frequent nutrient balancing while accommodating trade-offs [5], may differ substantially in yield and economic performance compared with decoupled aquaponics where the aquaculture and hydroponic components operate as separate entities.

In another study based on a survey, authors compared cross-country differences between Australia and Israel, assessing consumer awareness, preferences, and willingness to pay (WTP) for

aquaponic products [18]. The authors assessed the key differences in food quality, WTP, health standards, and the "organic" status of aquaponic products across the two countries. However, there is still a significant knowledge gap in the economic viability of these systems under varying biological configurations, the performance of such configurations in different climatic regions, and selective optimization of regional or climatic configurations to unlock the potential susceptibility or success of the food production systems. Although several studies have investigated economic viability within specific regions and at various production scales, there is a lack of a comprehensive empirical data-based review that compares economic outcomes and yield across diverse geographical climates and system types to predict the feasibility of soilless production under various conditions and system types.

Therefore, our study aims to address the knowledge gaps above by: (1) comparing the profitability of aquaponic (coupled and decoupled) and hydroponic systems across global climate zones and system types using metrics such as yield, net returns, benefit–cost ratio (BCR), and payback periods; (2) investigating the magnitude of influence of key system components—including input costs and biophysical variables—on economic outcomes using decision trees, effect sizes, correlation analysis, and PCA; and (3) introducing a novel calculator as a prototype, which over time—and with the integration of validated data, will develop the capacity to predict economic outcomes based on system-specific parameters across various climate zones, using compiled metadata and integrated datasets.

2 | Materials and Methodology

2.1 | Literature Search

Research articles were searched through online databases, Web of Science and Scopus. To ensure a comprehensive search, a search strategy was employed using a combination of keywords and Boolean operators ("AND" and "OR"). On both Scopus and Web of Science, the search strings used were: "economic viability" OR "cost–benefit analysis" OR "economic feasibility" OR "economics" OR "profitability" OR "economic analysis" OR "financial viability" OR "economic evaluation" AND "hydroponics" OR "aquaponics" OR "soilless system" AND "aeroponics" OR "coupled aquaponics" AND "media-bed" OR "substrate system" AND "nutrient film technique" OR "drip systems" AND "raft" OR "floating raft systems" OR "deep water culture" AND "Fish" OR "Tilapia" OR "*Oreochromis niloticus*" AND "African catfish" OR "*Clarias gariepinus*" AND "Lettuce" OR "*Lactuca sativa*" AND "Basil" OR "*Ocimum basilicum*." The search strings were adapted to fit into the query requirements of each database.

These selected keywords were required to either be present in the title or the abstract of the articles, narrowing down the search results to reflect the significant content of the articles related to the economic viability of the food production systems. We further searched through the relevant cross-relevant references within the selected articles and included them if such an article fits the search requirements. No restrictions were placed on the year of publication to enable a comprehensive scope of studies for data analysis.

The search results were narrowed down to aquaponics and hydroponics studies evaluating vegetable (and fish in the case of aquaponics) production over at least 1 year and further reporting input costs and corresponding revenue at the end of the production cycles. However, studies reporting either input costs or revenue were also considered. Studies that modeled economic scenarios without empirical or experimental data were excluded. Additionally, studies focusing on using plants to remove contaminants from wastewater (phytoremediation), with minimal focus on the yield of the products, were not considered in this study.

A total of 501 articles were obtained from the initial search, 191 of which were duplicates and were excluded from abstract and full-text screening. The remaining 310 were further refined based on the following criteria: (a) The study reports an initial experimental-based evaluation; (b) the study reports productivity of at least one plant species; (c) the study reports at least a complete annual cycle of yield, input, and/or output values; and (d) the study reports grow bed area or provides variables enabling calculation of grow bed area and stocking density (for aquaponics). Following the screening, 60 final articles were included for data extraction. To ensure a clean dataset, the selection and screening of these articles were carried out following a PRISMA-like approach [19].

2.2 | Data Extraction

The crops and fish yields per year, the biological parameters, the capital input cost, and the operational cost for each study were summarized in Excel. To ensure consistency, the data were extracted by two reviewers following a standardized Excel template. The biological parameters extracted include the regional address where the study was conducted, the types of hydroponics (e.g., raft, NFT) and aquaponics (coupled or decoupled), fish and plant species, grow bed area, stocking density information, water volume, and tank volumes. The location of the conducted studies stated in each study was traced to the Köppen–Geiger climate classification to collect the climate data [20]. The rationale behind using climate zones instead of countries is the existence of varying climates in a country and the opportunity to assess the similarities and differences in trends across various climates.

The capital investment cost includes a greenhouse, tanks, grow beds, pumps and blowers, a filtration unit, a pump, and aeration. Operational costs were also extracted, including those for fertilizer, labor, energy (electricity and gas), fish feed, fingerlings, and water. In studies that had missing data on grow bed area but had plant density and number of plants, areas were estimated where possible. For studies where cost data were reported in currencies other than USD, values were converted to USD using the average exchange rate when the study was conducted. Historical exchange rates were sourced from XE Currency Converter [21] to ensure accuracy and consistency across studies. Since costs and revenues at different regions and time series cannot be directly equated, and to understand the effects of the cost inputs on the total cost and input structure, the percentage contribution of each input to the total capital cost and operational cost was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Input cost share (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Individual input cost}}{\text{Total capital or operational cost}} \right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Similarly, in cases where studies do not report crop or fish yields directly, a crop-cut method was employed to calculate yield per square meter per year.

$$\text{Yield (kg/m}^2\text{/year)} = \frac{\text{Total harvested weight}}{\text{Grown bed area (m}^2\text{)}} \times \text{number of cycles per year} \quad (2)$$

Additionally, to compare the economic potential of soilless system products with soil-based systems, we compared the breakeven prices of the most commonly studied vegetable (lettuce) with the current prices in different countries or regions. The average current prices were obtained from Tridge (<https://www.tridge.com/>) for May 2025. The higher limit of the prices provided on the website was used for this study's analysis. The breakeven prices were either directly extracted from the studies or calculated (when not provided) using the formula:

$$\text{Breakeven price (USD/kg)} = \frac{\text{Total variable cost per square meter (USD)}}{\text{Yield per square meter (kg)}} \quad (3)$$

Other economic metrics such as the payback period (the ratio of initial investment cost to annual net return) and the BCR (the ratio of total revenue and total variable cost) were collected directly from the studies and used in the meta-analysis as recorded.

2.3 | Analytical Frameworks

The current study adopted various analytical frameworks to identify the factors driving the economic performance of the soilless systems, including descriptive statistics, regression modeling, machine-learning-based classification, and multivariate similarity analysis. The meta-analysis focused on aquaponics and hydroponics as soilless, as there are limited studies on the other soilless systems such as aeroponics, floconics, and others. In the present study, systems were classified as economically viable when the BCR was greater than 1, net return was greater than 0, and the payback period was less than 5 years. These thresholds were adopted from aquaponic and hydroponic economic studies such as Sunny et al. [22], Pinho et al. [23], Castilho-Barros et al. [24], and Quagraine et al. [25].

2.3.1 | Descriptive and Comparative Analysis

Descriptive statistics were employed to establish the distribution of economic metrics (e.g., BCR and payback periods) and biological parameters (e.g., grow bed area, stocking densities, plant species, and fish species) across various climate zones. Boxplots and barplots were generated to visualize and compare performance differences across various system types and climate zones. To compare the efficiency of soilless systems with conventional systems, we created barplots comparing the average annual yield per square meter obtained from our

dataset with the yield of a common plant (lettuce) using FAO data across different regions [26]. The countries in the plot were based on countries with at least three data points in our dataset.

2.3.2 | Regression and Multivariate Analysis to Identify the Factors Influencing Profitability and the Magnitude of Their Impacts

Linear and polynomial regressions were employed to investigate the factors influencing profitability and distribution of cost. We assessed the relationship between the percentage distribution of input costs (e.g., labor and energy cost) and net returns per square meter, which were then stratified by system types and climate zones. R^2 (coefficient of determination) and p values were used to evaluate the trends' strength and statistical significance. Studies with incomplete economic data were excluded from the quantitative models to avoid inconsistency.

Additionally, cosine similarity analysis was performed to identify system or structural similarities across climate zones, crops, and fish species, system types, and economic outcomes. Cosine similarity matrices were generated for the whole dataset and the aquaponics subset, allowing for hierarchical clustering. Hydroponics data were excluded due to limited data.

To quantify and evaluate the influence of these variables on economic performances, a multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was performed. Partial eta squared (η^2) values, a measure of effect sizes, were used to assess the magnitude of the effects of essential predictors such as system types, climate zones, and crop categories on economic metrics, including net return, BCR, and payback period.

2.3.3 | Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to Explore Input Contributions and System Dispersion

We further explored patterns in the multidimensional cost and yield and the contribution of various variables to a principal component; PCA was adopted. We assessed the influence of various variables on the entire dataset by identifying their spread and clustering. These variables include biological parameters such as yields, grow bed area, tank volumes, plant and fish species, climate zones, and hydroponic types, as well as economic parameters such as total variable cost, total capital cost, labor cost, energy cost, and net returns.

2.3.4 | Categorization of Performance Levels Using Decision Tree Classification

To identify the key indicators of economic performance, we used a decision tree classifier to group outcomes from different climates and system types into low, medium, and high profit. Plant yield per square meter, crop diversities, system type, climate zones, total variable cost per square meter, and total revenue per square meter were the input variables used to generate the decision tree.

Using multiple linear regression models, we predicted the effects of biological and economic inputs on system profitability.

Variables such as yields, grow bed and tank volumes, total revenue per square meter, and total variable cost per square meter were employed as the predictor variables. To identify statistically significant contributors, 95% confidence intervals and coefficients were plotted. The statistical analysis and data visualization performed in the study were performed using the ggplot package in R statistical software [27]. The decision trees were generated using the rpart package in R. To avoid overfitting, we constrained the maximum tree depth to four [28]. The complex parameter was optimized using the built-in 10-fold cross-validation procedure in the rpart, and the final trees were pruned at the complexity parameter value that minimized cross-validated error [29, 30]. We applied default control settings for minimum split size (20 observations) and minimum bucket size (7 observations). This approach, grounded in standard CART methodology, was employed to ensure that only robust and reproducible splits were retained [29]. The scripts and dataset used for the analysis in the present study will be made available upon reasonable request.

2.4 | Development of Soilless Systems Decision Support Calculator

The current study developed an interactive Excel-based economic decision support tool ("APECO") to facilitate the practical application of results obtained from the meta-data analysis. APECO was developed as a proof-of-concept decision-support framework that allows for the integration of economic data from different aquaponic and hydroponic configurations and climate zones. The calculator allows users to select system types, climate zones (based on Köppen classification), hydroponic types, and crop and fish species. Embedded, modifiable lookup tables generated from the meta-dataset and user-supplied local input, such as unit prices, grow bed area, and tank volume per grow bed area, enable yield predictions and potential annual revenue. The average variable cost per m^2 per year is adjusted based on climate, system type, and crop/fish species. Since the cost data used in the calculator were derived from studies conducted in different years, it was not standardized for global price fluctuations. Users with pre-knowledge of system outputs are encouraged to override the default estimates by supplying current data. The file is protected with a password, "APECO," to protect the formulas from being mistakenly erased. The calculator is currently limited by excluding capital costs, which were omitted due to significant variations in system components and operational setups. The calculator is available as open-access material in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15854313>).

3 | Results

3.1 | Overview of Study Distribution on Economic Viability in Soilless Systems

We assessed the percentage distribution of crop species, fish species, and climate zones in which most studies on economic viability were conducted. About ~35% of the studies were carried out in the tropical savannah (Aw) climate zone (Figure 1). This was followed by Cfb (temperate, no dry season, warm summer), Cfa (temperate, no dry season, hot summer), and Dfa (cold, no dry season,

FIGURE 1 | Barplot showing the percentage distribution of the climate zones of studies on the economic viability of soilless systems ($n = 145$). The climate zones were categorized based on the Köppen–Geiger system. Climate zone information: Dfa = cold, no dry season, hot summer; Aw = tropical, savannah; Cfa = temperate, no dry season, hot summer; Am = tropical, monsoon; Cfb = temperate, no dry season, warm summer; CSa = temperate, dry summer, hot summer; and Dfa = cold, no dry season, hot summer.

hot summer), with percentage distributions of 14.1%, 12.8%, and 12.2%, respectively. Other climate zones represented include CSa (temperate, dry summer, hot summer), a combined category of Dfa + Dfb + Cfa, BWh (arid, desert, hot), and Am (tropical, monsoon), with percentages of 9.7%, 5.6%, 2.8%, and 2.8%, respectively. The least represented climate zones in economic viability studies were BSk (arid, steppe, cold) and BSh (arid, steppe, hot), each accounting for 0.7% of observations. With the dominance of studies in tropical savannah (Aw) and temperate oceanic (Cfb), the empirical research on soilless systems' economic viability is concentrated in warm and mildly humid regions.

In terms of plant species used in economic viability studies, lettuce is the most widely studied, with 23.4% of the total observations. Other commonly studied species are tomato (13.5%), basil (8.5%), and milkweed (3.5%) (Figure S1). The percentage distribution of others, such as spinach, kale, pak choi, mint, parsley, and thyme, was less than 1%. In the studies involving aquaponics, the most commonly studied fish species in economic viability studies are Nile Tilapia (44%), African catfish (8.3%), Rainbow trout (6.4%), and hybrid Tilapia (4.5%) (Figure S2). Other species are Barramundi (4.6%), Whiteleg shrimp (4.6%), Murray cod (2.8%), and polyculture (> 2 species) (7.3%). The hydroponic system types mainly used in these studies are FRS (floating Raft System), Media-bed, NFT (Nutrient Film Technique), and combined NFT and FRS with percentage distribution of 44%, 17.5%, 15.4%, and 3.5%, respectively (Figure S3).

3.2 | Comparisons on Yield and Profitability Across Climate Zones and System Systems

The yield and profitability varied across different climate zones. The data suggested that the highest reported annual lettuce yield was recorded in CSa, with an average of $74.3 \pm 18.2 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$. The

average annual lettuce yield reported in Aw, Cfa, Cfb, and Dfa was 57.5 ± 75.4 , 55.3 ± 26.52 , 36.7 ± 64.4 , and $14 \pm 0.0 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$, respectively (Figure 2A). There was insufficient data on BSh and BSk. Similarly, tomato yield appeared highest in Cfa ($136.0 \pm 76.3 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$), although this was based on a limited sample size, followed by Cfb ($37.9 \pm 15.3 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$), and CSa ($32.74 \pm 57.59 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$). Fish yield differed between aquaponic configurations (Figure S4). Tilapia appeared as the most widely cultured species in the dataset (44%), with average yields of $294.81 \pm 974.86 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ in coupled systems and $305.34 \pm 351.33 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ in decoupled systems.

Regarding profitability, we compared BCR and payback period across the system types, climate zones, and hydroponic types. The highest mean BCR was recorded in the Dfb climate zone (2.1 ± 0.03). Others are Am (1.8 ± 0.4), Dfa (1.3 ± 0.25), Aw (1.29 ± 0.8), and Cfa (1.1 ± 0.62) (Figure 3A). The lowest BCR was recorded in Cfb (0.5 ± 0.26). Similarly, BCR varies across the hydroponic types. The highest (1.7 ± 0.8) mean BCR was recorded in the NFT hydroponic system type. The FRS and media bed have a similar average BCR of 1.3 ± 0.4 , followed by Kratky with a BCR of 0.7 ± 0.6 (Figure S5). On the other hand, the average BCR of crops grown in hydroponics (1.4 ± 1.32) was non-significant from those grown in aquaponics (1.3 ± 1.22) (Figure S6). In terms of production systems, coupled aquaponics had the lowest average BCR (1.3 ± 0.45) compared with hydroponic systems (1.7 ± 1.2) (Figure 3B).

In terms of system types, aquaponics showed higher reported yields for lettuce and tomatoes ($32.1 \pm 26.3 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$) compared to hydroponic systems ($18.4 \pm 20 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$) (Figure S7A), although these results may be a reflection of an imbalanced dataset and should be interpreted cautiously. We also compared the yield of these lettuce and tomato plants across various hydroponic types. The average yield was highest ($65 \pm 7.6 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$) in mixed-hydroponic systems, followed by

FIGURE 2 | Boxplot showing an estimated annual yield (lettuce, tomatoes, and basil) across various climate zones (A) and aquaponic types (B) in economic viability studies. Standalone hydroponics (HP) was included in the aquaponic type comparisons solely for comparative purposes. The climate zone categorization is based on the Köppen classification, which is obtained from individual study location information. The yield consists of various plant yields recorded over 12 months ($n = 145$). The dashed lines (as in BSh) indicate insufficient data. Na indicates data from regions whose locations were not stated. Climate zone information: Aw = tropical, savannah; Cfa = temperate, no dry season, hot summer; Cfb = temperate, no dry season, warm summer; CSa = temperate, dry summer, hot summer; and Dfa = cold, no dry season, hot summer.

media-bed ($44.9 \pm 36.4 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$) and NFT ($32.7 \pm 22.5 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$) (Figure S7B).

Another economic metric explored is the payback period, which quantifies the initial investment ratio to the annual net cash flow. In the current study, the least (1.54 ± 1.2) payback period was recorded in Aw. Others include Cfa + Aw (2.25 ± 0.5), CSa (5 ± 0.7), Cfa (6.08 ± 2.4), Dfa (7.18 ± 0.9), and Cfb (15 ± 10.44) (Figure 4A). Payback periods differed across production systems, with the longest payback period observed in decoupled aquaponics (7.9 ± 0.3 years), followed by coupled aquaponics (4.7 ± 2.3 years), and standalone hydroponics (3.7 ± 2.0 years) (Figure 4B). However, given the limited representation of decoupled systems, these differences should be interpreted cautiously. Regarding the hydroponic types, a combined system of various hydroponic types has the least (1.11 ± 0.13) payback period, followed by FRS (3.31 ± 1.89), channel-based (5.33 ± 0.58), NFT (6.2 ± 1.6), and media-bed (7.5 ± 1.56) (Figure S8).

Furthermore, we compared the average annual yield of lettuce in soilless systems (aquaponics + hydroponics) with corresponding soil-based yield data from FAO dataset of lettuce crop production for 2023 (Figure 5). Across the selected countries, soilless systems generally showed higher average annual lettuce yields compared to soil-based systems, with the highest observed in Italy (74.25 kg m^{-2}). However, these comparisons are based on limited data points ($n \leq 3$ per country) and should therefore be

regarded as indicative rather than definitive. In contrast, the average annual lettuce yield per square meter from soil-based systems was 2.4 kg m^{-2} . The lowest yield among the countries from the soilless systems was recorded in Australia, with 13.4 kg . This was, however, significantly higher than the soil-based system value (1.71 kg m^{-2}).

3.3 | Factors Influencing Economic Viability in Soilless Systems Across Various Climate Zones and System Types

3.3.1 | Economic Drivers in Aquaponic Systems

The sensitivity analysis to investigate parameters influencing farmers' annual net returns showed variations among aquaponics' economic and biological parameters (Figure 6). Plant revenue showed the strongest positive association with net returns, with an estimated standardized coefficient close to +1. Other variables that were positively associated with net return were fish revenue, plant yield, total capital cost, and fish tank volume. In contrast, operational cost was most strongly associated with lower net returns, having a negative coefficient close to -1. Other variables showing negative impacts on net returns are labor cost and fish yield. Although the cost of grow beds and grow bed area showed a positive point estimate, the wide confidence intervals indicate high uncertainty, suggesting these associations should

FIGURE 3 | Boxplot showing the distribution of benefit–cost ratios (BCR) of soilless farming systems across different Köppen–Geiger climate zones (A) and production systems (B) ($n = 38$). BCR values represent the ratio of total revenue to total cost, with outliers excluded using the interquartile range (IQR) method. The aquaponic type included in the analysis was coupled aquaponics, as data from decoupled aquaponics were insufficient. Climate zone information: Dfa = cold, no dry season, hot summer; Aw = tropical, savannah; Cfa = temperate, no dry season, hot summer; Am = tropical, monsoon; Cfb = temperate, no dry season, warm summer; CSa = temperate, dry summer, hot summer; and Dfa = cold, no dry season, hot summer.

be interpreted with caution. On the other hand, the unit price showed a significant positive coefficient close to +0.5.

3.3.2 | The PCA of Economic and Biophysical Variables

To investigate the differential contributions of various economic and biophysical variables in aquaponics and hydroponics, PCA was employed. In Dimension 1 (Dim1) of the coupled aquaponics, the largest variance in the dataset was explained by energy cost (17.7%), total variable cost (16%), plant revenue (11.8%), hydroponic type (11.8%), labor cost (8.6%), and plant yield (8.5%). In contrast, the greatest proportion of variance in Dim2 was accounted for by total revenue (30.2%), net returns (19.4%), total capital cost (11.5%), plant yield (10.3%), and climate zones (7%) (Figure 7A). For the decoupled aquaponics, Dim1 was driven by plant revenue, total revenue, energy cost, plant yield, and total variable cost, which were the largest contributors to variance, with contributions of 17.4%, 16.9%, 15%, 14.7%, and 12%, respectively (Figure 7B). These variance contributions highlight patterns of co-variation between the selected variables, but given dataset limitations, the results should be viewed as exploratory rather than definitive.

To corroborate the result of the PCA, a pairwise relationship among the variables was assessed using a cosine similarity heat map (Figure 8). In the coupled aquaponic systems, net returns showed strong positive associations with total revenue and plant revenue (cosine similarity of 0.75 and 0.71, respectively).

In contrast, net return showed a negative but weak association with labor cost (cosine similarity = -0.18) and energy cost (cosine similarity = -0.08) (Figure 8A). In terms of cost, total variable cost showed a strong positive alignment with labor cost (cosine similarity = 0.72), energy cost (cosine similarity = 0.65), and TCP (cosine similarity = 0.6). Climate zone showed strong positive associations with plant species (cosine similarity = 0.69) and country (cosine similarity = 0.75), and a weaker association with net return (cosine similarity = 0.31), suggesting possible regional clustering rather than a direct effect.

On the other hand, net returns in decoupled aquaponic systems were positively associated with labor cost (cosine similarity = 0.72), energy cost (cosine similarity = 0.64), and TCP (cosine similarity = 0.6) (Figure 8B). Net returns also showed weaker associations with plant revenue (0.23) and plant yield (0.11). However, inconsistencies in the associations—for example, net returns aligning negatively with TVC (-0.04)—likely reflect the limited dataset ($n = 15$) rather than stable patterns. Similarly, in the standalone hydroponics analysis, net returns showed strong positive associations with TVC (cosine similarity = 0.99), energy cost (cosine similarity = 0.98), and TCP (cosine similarity = 0.98) (Figure S12).

The relationship and interaction between the variables were further analyzed using a regression plot to see the relationship between the labor/energy cost per square meter and net returns in aquaponics. Regression analysis indicated a

FIGURE 4 | Boxplots showing payback period across climate zones (A) and production system configurations (B). Outliers were removed using the interquartile range (IQR) method. Payback periods varied among climate zones and differed between coupled and decoupled aquaponics, as well as standalone hydroponics (HP). The boxes represent interquartile range with median values, with the whiskers indicating variability outside the upper and lower quartiles. The dashed lines indicate insufficient data. “Multiple” indicates combinations of more than two hydroponic types. Sample sizes are $n = 42$ (coupled = 27; HP = 10; decoupled = 5). The dashed lines indicate insufficient data. Climate zone information: Dfa = cold, no dry season, hot summer; Aw = tropical, savannah; Cfa = temperate, no dry season, hot summer; Am = tropical, monsoon; Cfb = temperate, no dry season, warm summer; CSa = temperate, dry summer, hot summer; and Dfa = cold, no dry season, hot summer.

FIGURE 5 | Barplot comparing the average annual yield of lettuce crop production per square meter between soilless (aquaponics and hydroponics) and soil-based systems across different countries (Australia, Ecuador, Italy, and the United States). The data from the soil-based systems were obtained from FAOSTAT, while the average soilless systems data per country were derived from this study’s dataset ($n \leq 3$).

strong negative association between labor cost and net returns ($R^2 = 0.95$, $p < 0.001$) (Figure 9). Although this suggests a comprehensive pattern in the dataset, the small sample size ($n = 20$) means the result should be interpreted with caution.

Regarding labor cost contributions to variable cost, there were disparities across the system types, with hydroponic systems having a higher percentage contribution ($54\% \pm 20.9\%$) compared to aquaponics ($39\% \pm 18.2\%$), at a statistical significance

FIGURE 6 | The standardized effects of biophysical, economic, and market variables on net returns of farmers in aquaponics ($n = 32$). Each point dash represents the standardized regression coefficient, and the horizontal bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. A strong influence on the net returns of variables is indicated by coefficients significantly different from zero (nonoverlapping red lines). TCP cost/m² indicates total capital cost per square meters. Comparisons between coupled and decoupled aquaponics were not conducted due to insufficient data from decoupled systems.

of $p = 0.0084$ ($\alpha = 0.05$). Similarly, the mean percentage contribution of labor cost also significantly varied across the types of hydroponics ($p = 0.004$), with the highest recorded in FRS ($65.4\% \pm 15.8\%$), followed by NFT ($46.22\% \pm 24.7\%$) and drip systems (38.06%) (Figure S9).

Energy or electricity cost is another essential component that varied across climate zones. In a similar pattern to labor cost, mean energy cost (as a percentage of the variable cost) was highest in temperate climates: Dfa ($30.96\% \pm 14.91\%$), Cfb ($30.45\% \pm 16.2\%$), and Cfa ($12.77\% \pm 8.1\%$) (Figure S10). In contrast, energy costs were lowest ($11.5\% \pm 16.39\%$) in tropical climates (Am and Aw). However, the result may reflect data imbalance, as the majority (~35%) of the dataset originated from tropical savannah (Aw), while some climate zones were represented by little or no data.

In the analysis of annual cost distributions as a percentage of the total variable costs, climate-related differences were suggested. In temperate climates such as Cfa, Cfb, and CSa, the largest shares were allocated to labor costs, with contributions ranging from 3.4%–55% (Figure 10A). However, the sample size of these individual climates was not sufficient enough to substantiate firm conclusions. In tropical climates such as Am, the feed cost accounted for the largest share, with a mean percentage of up to 59.5%. Energy cost also contributed substantially to TVC: 33.9% in Cfb and 30.5% in Dfa, compared with 11.2% in Am and 10% in Aw. Similarly, this result should be interpreted with caution due to data imbalance across the climate zones.

When comparing the cost contributions to TVC between coupled and decoupled aquaponics, labor costs were the highest contributor in both configurations, accounting for 27.2% and 29%, respectively (Figure 10B). Energy costs slightly contributed higher in coupled aquaponics (17.3%) compared to the decoupled system (14.5%). Although feed costs also contributed marginally more to TVC in coupled aquaponics (22%) than in decoupled aquaponics (19.1%), these results should be interpreted with caution, as decoupled systems accounted for only 9% of the dataset.

Regarding the interactions among input and cash flow variables in aquaponics, several statistically significant relationships were observed (Figure S11). There was a strong positive correlation between the net return and yield ($r = 0.58$, $p < 0.001$), and a strong negative correlation between net return and total variable cost ($r = -0.45$, $p < 0.001$). Additionally, a strong internal collinearity relationship was observed between energy cost and total variable cost ($r = 84$, $p < 0.001$). On the other hand, climate zones showed a strong negative correlation with plant yield ($r = -0.42$, $p < 0.001$), and a strong positive correlation with hydroponic type ($r = 0.66$, $p < 0.001$).

3.4 | Decision Tree and the Effects of Different Variables on Performances of System Types

To explore how key explanatory variables such as variable cost, net return, climate zones, hydroponic types, and plant yield,

FIGURE 7 | Principal component analysis (PCA) biplot showing various economic and biophysical variables' contributions to coupled (A) and decoupled (B) aquaponics dataset variations ($n=70$). The arrows or vectors represent the loadings of the variables, while the points represent the systems (orange points indicate aquaponics and green points indicate hydroponics). The presented Dim1 and Dim2 capture the major dimensions of variability in the dataset. HP type indicates the type of hydroponic systems, total VC indicates total variable cost, and TCP indicates total capital cost. All cost and revenue variables are expressed as per square meters.

are associated with economic outcomes of aquaponics, we employed decision tree analysis to compare coupled and decoupled aquaponics. In the coupled aquaponics, profitability patterns were most strongly associated with climate zone, plant yield, fish yield, and total revenue (Figure 11A). Fish yield emerged as a key splitting variable, as systems producing at $\leq 102.2 \text{ kgm}^{-3}$ were more frequently unprofitable, while those producing

higher fish yields—especially $> 811.4 \text{ kgm}^{-3}$ were more often profitable. In addition, high TVC was associated with lower likelihood of positive net returns. Gini (feature-importance) ranked variables as TVC (30.3%), climate zone (25.7%), fish yield (23.7%), total revenue (16.2%), and plant yield (4.1%). The model indicated that climate zone, which formed the root split, co-varied with downstream nodes, as systems from CSa (hot-summer

FIGURE 8 | Legend on next page.

FIGURE 8 | A cosine similarity heat map showing the interrelations between the variables in (A) coupled aquaponics ($n = 41$) and (B) decoupled aquaponics ($n = 15$). The closer the cosine value is to 1, the stronger the directional alignment between the two variables. The hydroponic panels do not include fish species. TCP and total VC indicate total capital cost and total variable cost, respectively.

FIGURE 9 | Regression plot showing the relationship between labor and energy cost per square meter and net returns in aquaponics ($n = 20$). The shaded areas represent 95% confidence intervals. The solid and dotted lines indicate linear regressions and second-order polynomial trends, respectively.

FIGURE 10 | A boxplot showing the distribution of key variable costs as a percentage of total variable cost (TVC) across different climate zones. The plot shows the variability in the share of annual costs involving fingerlings, feed, labor, energy, fertilizer, and water costs ($n = 369$). Indicated in the boxplots are the median, interquartile range, and the potential outliers within each cost category. Climate zone information (Dfa = cold, no dry season, hot summer; Aw = tropical, savannah; Cfa = temperate, no dry season, hot summer; Am = tropical, monsoon; Cfb = temperate, no dry season, warm summer; CSa = temperate, dry summer, hot summer; and Dfa = cold, no dry season, hot summer).

A

B

FIGURE 11 | (A) A decision tree showing the classification of the profitability performances of coupled aquaponic systems ($n = 64$). Variables such as hydroponic types, plant yield, climate zones, total variable cost (VC) per square meter, net return, and total revenue were used. The terminal nodes indicate profitability outcomes, identifying economically viable production scenarios. The nodes show gini impurity (which is a measure of classification purity, where 0 indicates perfect separation), samples (number of systems), and distribution of profitable versus non-profitable outcomes. (B) A decision tree showing the classification of the profitability performances of decoupled aquaponic systems ($n = 15$). Variables such as hydroponic types, plant yield, climate zones, total variable cost (VC) per square meter, net return, and total revenue were used. The terminal nodes indicate profitability outcomes, identifying economically viable production scenarios. The nodes show gini impurity (which is a measure of classification purity, where 0 indicates perfect separation), samples (number of systems) and distribution of profitable versus non-profitable outcomes.

mediterranean) showed profitability patterns compared with other climate zones.

The decoupled model on the other hand produced a far fewer splits, with thresholds emerging only for plant yield and total revenue. The absence of fish yield as a splitting variable is likely due to the very limited dataset ($n=15$). Hence, the thresholds should be considered less stable and more explanatory than those observed in coupled systems. Although profitability appeared to hinge on a revenue threshold, as systems with total revenue $\leq \$128.7\text{m}^{-2}$ were uniformly unprofitable, whereas those earning above this threshold were generally profitable when plant yield exceeded 28.3kg m^{-2} —these patterns should be interpreted cautiously due to the small sample size and may not be generalizable.

3.5 | Comparisons of Breakeven Prices and Current Prices of Lettuce Across Countries

The comparisons of breakeven prices and current prices of lettuce show substantial variations across the selected countries. In the Philippines, Brazil, and Uganda, the average market prices exceed the breakeven prices, suggesting a positive margin for aquaponically grown lettuce (Figure 12A). In contrast, there was a huge difference between breakeven and current prices in the United States and Belgium. For example, the mean breakeven price of lettuce produced in the United States was $\$9.69$, whereas the average current price was $\$3.83$, indicating negative margins. Breakeven prices also varied across production systems (Figure 12B). In tomato cultivation, the lowest mean breakeven price was observed in coupled aquaponics ($\$2.24 \pm \0.52 , $n=2$),

FIGURE 12 | (A) Comparisons of the breakeven prices of lettuce with the average current prices (May 2025) across various countries (United States [US], Italy, Philippines, Australia, Ecuador, Uganda, Belgium, and Brazil). The average current prices of lettuce per kg were obtained from Tridge for May 2025 (<https://www.tridge.com/>). The breakeven prices were obtained by dividing the mean total variable cost per m^2 by the yield per m^2 (kg) across the countries. The rationale behind the selected countries was due to the availability of sufficient data in the selected countries (with at least three data points). (B) Mean breakeven price by production system—coupled (single-loop aquaponics), decoupled (double-loop aquaponics), and HP (standalone hydroponics; non-aquaponic control)—for tomato and lettuce. Bars are means across studies; error bars denote ± 1 SD where available ($n=40$).

followed by decoupled aquaponics ($\$5.44 \pm \4.96 , $n=10$) and standalone hydroponics ($\$5.89 \pm \3.08 , $n=5$). The difference in sample sizes among the systems is an indication that these results should be interpreted with caution. For lettuce, the lowest mean breakeven price was recorded in standalone hydroponic systems ($\$3.12 \pm \1.30 , $n=7$), whereas coupled aquaponics averaged 9.17 ± 11.80 ($n=14$). In decoupled aquaponics, lettuce mean breakeven price was $\$0.10$, but this was based on a single observation ($n=1$) and should therefore be interpreted with caution.

3.6 | A Decision Support Calculator to Assess the Economic Viability of Proposed Soilless Systems

To reduce economic losses in soilless systems, we developed a prototype of an Excel-based tool (APECO) that allows users to assess and evaluate the economic viability of soilless systems under different configurations. The tool integrates production inputs such as hydroponic types, crop yield, climate zones, and cost parameters to generate key financial metrics, including profitability status, total revenue, and breakeven price. The profitability status is classified based on a decision tree model using the dataset from this study, which highlights the critical relationship between plant yield, variable cost, and total revenue.

In addition, the profitability classification is supported by comparing the calculated breakeven price with current market prices to determine whether aquaponic products could compete in the market without an organic label. It is important to note that the prices and costs used are subject to change over time; therefore, users are encouraged to input context-specific values such as local unit prices for fish and vegetables. Similarly, users may override the predicted cost and yield values—such as variable cost per m^2 and yield per m^2 —with more contextually accurate data based on their interests and assumptions.

Importantly, APECO should be regarded as a prototype tool. It has not been validated against real-world data, and its output should be considered exploratory until further empirical testing is carried out.

4 | Discussion

4.1 | The Overview of the Economic Viability of Soilless Systems Across Climate Zones and System Types

Our study highlights that system configurations, ambient climate, and cultivation variables are important factors associated with the profitability of aquaponic and hydroponic systems. Financial metrics such as BCR, payback periods, and net returns varied significantly across the selected system types and climate zones. The lowest yields—lettuce, tomatoes, and basil—were recorded in the Dfa, Dfb, and Cfa climate zones, but these may reflect the relatively small sample sizes from the temperate climates compared to the tropical climate such as Aw. For instance, the yield of lettuce grown in FRS systems within these climate zones (Dfa, Dfb, and Cfa) was estimated at an average of $1.32 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$, compared to approximately $3.7 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$

estimated in Aw (tropical savannah) zones. Most of the data from these temperate and cold zones originated from the Midwestern United States, where extremely cold weather conditions increase heating requirements, limiting organic cultivation and raising costs for temperature regulation. This may explain the relatively lower yields recorded in these climate zones. For example, Bailey et al. [31] reported a lettuce yield of $59.6 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$ in the Virgin Islands, US (an Aw region), compared with $1.3 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$ recorded in the Midwestern US by Quagraine et al. [25]. It should be noted, however, that while the present study categorized systems based on climate zones established by Köppen–Geiger classification, labor regulations, energy subsidies, and broader political and socioeconomic contexts can also substantially influence both operational cost and investment costs. These factors may vary across the climate zones but were beyond the scope of this study.

Aside from climate effects, aquaponic system configuration also appeared to shape profitability patterns. In coupled systems, net-return was strongly associated with revenue-side variables, showing positive alignment with total revenue and plant revenue while exhibiting negative alignment with energy and labor costs. Although the net returns of decoupled aquaponics, aligned with cost-side variables, including labor cost, energy cost, and total capital cost, the data imbalance—only 9% of the dataset represented decoupled systems—limits the ability to draw concrete conclusions from this result.

In terms of system types, although aquaponics systems reported higher yields for lettuce ($53.65 \pm 39.44 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$) and tomatoes ($72.87 \pm 59.68 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$) compared to hydroponics (34.8 ± 14.4 and $29 \pm 21 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$, respectively), these differences were not statistically significant. Regarding system configurations, although a higher mean tomato yield per m^2 was observed in coupled aquaponics compared to decoupled aquaponics systems, and a higher mean lettuce yield was recorded in decoupled aquaponics, these discrepancies may be the result of data imbalance between the two system configurations in the dataset. The latter, however, generally allows for more precise nutritional control which can foster improved plant growth compared to coupled systems, where control over nutrient solution is limited. Studies such as Chandrou et al. [32] and Monsees et al. [33] recorded higher yield of lettuce grown in decoupled aquaponics compared to those grown in coupled systems and standalone hydroponics. Similarly, Maxwell et al. [34] reported higher yield of lettuce (3.31 kg m^{-2}) in aquaponics compared to hydroponics (2.31 kg m^{-2}) over a 45-day period. However, no difference was observed in lettuce yield between aquaponics systems (with varying stocking densities of Nile Tilapia) and hydroponic systems [31].

The present study showed that percentage contribution of energy cost appears to vary across climate zones, reaching 30%–33.5% in the temperate climates, compared to 10%–11.5% in the tropical ones. Although this discrepancy may be partly attributed to relatively higher temperature regulations required in the temperate climates, other factors such as technological efficiency, subsidy policies, and energy pricing structures can also substantially influence energy costs across regions [10, 12]. Mugo-Bundi et al. [35] in Kenya and Castilho-Barros et al. [24] in Brazil reported that energy cost accounted for ~4% and 14% of

operational cost, respectively. In contrast, energy cost accounted for 24% in Germany [36] and 27% in the temperate region of Spain [24]. Corroborating this, labor costs contributed more than 40% of total variable costs in both aquaponic and hydroponic systems [12, 36, 37]. These high input shares may explain the extended payback periods and relatively low BCRs reported for soilless production systems across temperate climate zones. However, these elevated costs are not solely attributable to climate, as factors such as market structure, levels of technological adoption, availability of subsidies for aquaponic products, local market dynamics, and policy frameworks and implementations can substantially influence profitability, which may co-vary across climate zones [38, 39]. For instance, while technological adoption and automation may hold promise for reducing labor burdens, their uptake is often constrained by capital, extension support, and farmer capacity [40]. Similarly, in small-scale aquaponics commonly adopted in tropical climates, family labors are often employed, and when properly accounted for, its value may shift apparent profitability into negative economic profit. Hence, these confounding factors underline the need for cautious interpretation of the climate-related patterns observed in the present study.

The comparison of payback periods between the coupled and decoupled aquaponic systems showed that the latter, on average, exhibited higher payback periods than the former. This outcome may be expected, as decoupled aquaponics generally incur higher capital and operational costs due to the need to operate both the aquaculture and hydroponic components independently. However, the data imbalance between the two system designs indicates that this result should be interpreted with caution. Studies such as Adler et al. [41], Baganz et al. [36], and Holliman et al. [42] reported payback periods ranging from 7 to 27 years for decoupled systems, while Ghamkhar et al. [43] and Quagraine et al. [25] reported shorter payback periods ranging from ~3 to 7 years for coupled systems.

Conclusively, emerging studies highlight the potential of automation and robotics to reduce labor costs in soilless systems. An IoT-enabled monitoring approach is being developed through machine learning to optimize the dosing of nutrients and pH, and detect the emergence of plant diseases [44–46]. Similarly, using robots for plant pruning, automated seeding, and harvesting is being suggested to reduce labor hours and, subsequently, costs related to labor. However, there are currently limited studies demonstrating a reduction in costs using these tools. In Zhao et al. [47], the authors investigated the reduction of energy consumption and cost in urban aquaponics by developing a model that optimises energy consumption through continuous, schedulable, and conditionally triggered loads categorization of equipment. The authors proposed a scheduling model which enables a shift or delay in the operation of electrical equipment to align with periods of lower electricity consumption and consequent electricity cost.

Despite the tropical climates having less energy and labor costs, the adaptability of the food production systems is still relatively limited. Benjamin et al. [48] and Folorunso et al. [15] have identified critical barriers such as inadequate technical know-how, power instability, high initial investment costs, direct adoption of temperate-centric system designs, and lack of access to input resources for hydroponic and aquaponic produce affecting

adaptability in the regions. For example, Benjamin et al. [48] recorded higher profitability from soilless systems relying on locally sourced inputs than those relying on foreign-sourced input resources. Despite their favorable environmental conditions, these constraints and a lack of localized economic assessments contribute to the underrepresentation of tropical zones in the global soilless agriculture discourse.

4.2 | The Impacts of Yield, Revenue, and Operational Cost on Profitability

Our result highlighted yield, variable cost, and revenue per square meter as the most significant predictors of the economic viability of soilless systems, ahead of other variables such as climate zones. The decision tree analysis showed that total revenue was strongly associated with profitability, suggesting that higher productivity is linked with improved economic outcomes. With a threshold of \$459 m⁻² per year, coupled systems generating less than this amount are more likely to be unprofitable, underscoring the importance of achieving a minimum revenue level as a prerequisite for economic sustainability. On the other hand, at a low revenue, plant yield emerged as the most important predictor variable, with systems recording $\leq 28.8 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$ found to be frequently unprofitable, highlighting the importance of biological activities in productivity. This is in line with previous studies where sensitivity analyses showed that systems initially recorded as unprofitable became economically viable with improved productivity. For example, Baganz et al. [10], which investigated the economic viability of Tilapia-tomato aquaponics in Germany, recorded a negative net return at an initial production rate of $16.7 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$. However, the authors recorded an estimated positive net return when yield increased to $41 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$. A similar result was recorded in Mugo-Bundi et al. [35].

The present study suggests that the relative contribution of plant versus fish-driven revenue in aquaponics seems to depend on system configuration (i.e., coupled and decoupled). In coupled systems, net return co-varied strongly with plant-side revenues while showing weak or negative alignment with labor and energy costs. In decoupled systems, net return is associated positively with TVC and TCP structures, with a weak positive alignment to plant revenue and plant yield; however, these patterns should be interpreted cautiously due to the limited representation of decoupled systems in the dataset. Although these patterns were consistent with the decision-tree analysis, in which fish yield was a major splitter for coupled aquaponics, units producing $\leq 102.2 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ were often unprofitable, whereas high fish yields ($> 811.4 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$) were associated with profitability. However, fish yield did not appear as a splitter in the decoupled tree, likely due to decoupled aquaponics' limited sample size, rather than lack of importance. Although the present study showed that improving revenue and plant yield may be the direct lever to increase profitability in coupled aquaponics, whereas reducing TVC and TCP may be comparatively more impactful in decoupled aquaponics, these patterns should be regarded as preliminary and hypothesis generating rather than definitive conclusions, given the under-representation of decoupled systems in the dataset ($n = 15$). Moreover, the observed cost-driven associations in

decoupled systems may reflect sample-specific characteristics rather than generalizable trends. Hence, future studies with larger datasets and more climate-diverse datasets will be necessary to complement and confirm these differences.

Although many studies exploring the projections of profitability of soilless systems use the impact of geometric price changes in the sensitivity analysis [12, 15], our findings suggest that increasing yield may be a more practical lever for profitability. This is particularly relevant given that price fluctuations are often beyond farmers' control—except in monopolized markets—especially where market demand and supply have not yet reached equilibrium. Moreover, changes in the price of key vegetables, such as lettuce, usually occur gradually rather than geometrically. For example, according to the US Bureau of Labour Statistics [49], the average retail price of iceberg lettuce only increased by 11% in 5 years, from \$1.29 per pound in 2020 to \$1.44 per pound in 2025. In addition, the assumption that a sole vegetable price change (while other input costs remain constant) does not usually reflect the complex dynamics of market conditions. Hence, sensitivity analysis focusing on proposed drastic price changes to justify the profitability of soilless system products may not be a good measure to forecast the systems' economic survival.

Although climate and hydroponic types are known to influence system productivity, they appeared less influential in the decision tree analysis. This may be due to the indirect effect of their impacts on economic viability. For example, the strong positive alignment between fish species, climate zones, and country could strongly indicate the influence of regional climatic regions on the output of the food production system but may not directly be attributed to profitability. Moreover, their primary effect on yield could be masked by economic viability, accounting for much of the variance exerted by the climate and system types.

4.3 | Breakeven Price Metric; a Reflection of Climatic and Economic Disparities?

The present study identified tropical countries such as Uganda, Brazil, and the Philippines as having higher profitability prospects for soilless lettuce production than countries like Belgium, Italy, and the United States. Although the former group is primarily located in tropical climates—where production systems often incur lower variable costs due to reduced labor and energy expenses—these conditions may contribute to lower breakeven prices, but they are not necessarily the sole predictor of profitability. Another determinant may be system configuration. The comparable labor dominance in total variable cost (27%–29%) and the slightly lower share of energy cost in decoupled systems (14.5%) compared to coupled systems' 17.3% may interact with price–yield regimes to influence breakeven outcomes, alongside TVC and TCP intensity. The breakeven price for tomatoes produced in decoupled aquaponics systems (~\$12 to \$14) [11, 36] was substantially higher than that reported for tomatoes produced in coupled systems (~\$2 to \$5) [42, 50]. However, the discrepancy may also be influenced by other factors, including climatic differences, regional policies, and yield volumes, among others. An alternative contributing factor could be the variations in production approaches. Tropical systems may employ

basic, low-cost methods compared to the high-end, controlled, and technologically advanced systems commonly used in temperate countries. For example, the use of the Kratky method in Uganda and basic deep water culture systems in Brazil may explain the lower total variable cost per m² reported at \$12.1 and \$105.73, respectively [23, 51]. The relative simplicity of tropical aquaponics may support cost-effective production. For example, in Bangladesh and Vietnam, the common use of net cages and earthen ponds topped with floating rafts to co-cultivate various local vegetables and fish species in both countries significantly reduces operational cost while alleviating pressures from substantial initial capital investment [22, 52, 53]. Similarly, studies from Nigeria have shown that substituting gravel substrates and unprocessed coconut coir for perlites or processed coconut coir in media bed systems improves water retention and mitigates challenges associated with interrupted power supply, while the use of other locally available materials further reduces both operational costs and capital cost intensity [15, 48, 54].

In contrast, more comprehensive systems such as the modified University of the Virgin Islands (UVI) model in the United States or the recently modeled decoupled systems (e.g., INAPRO and BICH) usually used in Germany, Belgium, and Australia have higher total variable costs, which may be due to systems' complexities and technological inputs [25, 55, 56]. However, despite the profitability recorded in case studies conducted in tropical climates, the adoption of soilless systems remains limited in these regions [2]. However, the apparent differences in the profitability of aquaponics between tropical and climate zones should be interpreted cautiously given that the dataset is dominated (~35%) by the tropical climate zone (Aw), while there is minimal data or a lack of data in some climate zones.

4.4 | Utilization of APECO

The APECO tool is presented here as an initial proof-of-concept prototype that integrates climate zones, system configurations, and production parameters to estimate key economic metrics. By calculating net returns and projecting profitability classifications, the tool has the potential to provide a preliminary overview of the economic viability of the intended production capacity and its configurations pending validation through real-world data and empirical trials. In addition, the tool will allow users to compare profitability across different scales, climates, and scenarios, serving as a pre-investment analysis tool. This feature has the potential to reduce economic risks and curtail the detrimental effects caused by loss of capital investment.

Based on the outcomes of the present study, APECO treats coupled, decoupled, and standalone hydroponic systems as distinct economic entities. In relation to the climate zones, the tool incorporates suggested mean values for vegetable yield per growing area per year, as well as fish yield per unit volume per year.

It is imperative to state that there are existing calculators for hydroponic and aquaponic systems, such as iFarm and Calculator Academy [57, 58]. However, these calculators mainly focus on addressing the input of variables such as

electricity, stocking and planting density, power, and water, leaving out detailed economic or profitability variables and metrics. Moreover, these calculators do not have tools to assess productivity across different system types, configurations, and climates. In addition, existing calculators are not integrated with time-sensitive or dynamically updated data sources.

An intended innovation of the APECO prototype is its user-friendly interface, designed to enable dynamic adjustments of economic and biological input parameters. This feature ensures that users can update and tailor inputs when the metadata does not accurately reflect current or local realities. In addition, the inclusion of lookup sheets and self-input sections in the calculator will enhance usage by allowing users to revise or update datasets in response to local realities, improving precision over time. Future versions of APECO may incorporate biological data such as water usage, energy consumption, stocking density, and capacity calculations to assist farmers—with little or no prior knowledge of the systems—in determining key variables for the initial setup.

It is important to state that the current version of APECO has not yet been validated against real-world operational data. Hence, its outputs should be regarded as illustrative and exploratory, pending future empirical validation. In addition, the calculator is presented as a proof-of-concept prototype, designed to demonstrate the feasibility and structure of a standardized economic calculator for soilless systems, rather than as a fully validated decision-support tool. Although this prototype generates configuration- and climate-specific profitability outputs, these should be regarded as illustrative, as capital investment inputs are not yet incorporated and the tool has not been validated through real-world trial applications. In the near future, we aim to incorporate capital investment structures—accounting for different system configurations—and to undertake field-based calibration to enhance both its reliability and practical relevance to stakeholders.

We plan to include an elaborate expansion of the inclusion of capital cost inputs, allowing users to select or input essential facilities such as greenhouse dimensions, area, and operational type; hydroponic system type; unit counts and dimensions, number and horsepower of pumps, monitoring systems, and the number and size of filtration units, fish tanks, and biofilters. Additional parameters, such as annual daylight hours and temperature ranges across the years will as well be incorporated. While default values will be suggested for different regions, users will have the flexibility to override them to better reflect their local realities. In addition, future versions aim to incorporate regional dynamic datasets such as energy tariffs, market prices, and labor regulations. We will also adapt the tool for scalability, enabling scenario testing across small-scale farmers and commercial scales, while incorporating feedback from farmers, researchers, and policy makers to enhance relevance and usability.

5 | Conclusions

For the first time, our study delved into the economic assessment of aquaponics systems using aggregated data across

diverse climate zones and production configurations. This study comprehensively synthesizes the economic viability of soilless systems—specifically aquaponics and hydroponics—by comparing diverse climate zones, system configurations, and production inputs. Aw and Am, which are tropical climates, were characterized by lower energy and labor costs, and appeared to perform economically better than temperate regions in terms of breakeven price and net return. However, this result may reflect broader structural and economic differences rather than the climate zones. In addition, the dataset is highly imbalanced, with a strong concentration of studies dominated by the tropical savannah (Aw), while data from other climate zones were sparse. Profitability patterns appeared to vary by system designs, as net returns in coupled aquaponics tended to be more closely associated with revenue-side variables, whereas in decoupled aquaponics, profitability seemed more dependent on cost structure, likely reflecting higher capital intensity and operational complexity. However, the discrepancy may be due to the relatively small sample size of the decoupled systems ($n = 15$). The findings also indicate that the production approach—whether based on high-input controlled environments or low-cost, basic systems—significantly shapes economic outcomes, independent of climate zone. While the available data in the present study suggest a trend toward higher profitability in tropical zones, largely due to lower labor and energy costs, this observation should be interpreted cautiously given the limited number of case studies and their restricted geographical coverage.

Our metadata analysis indicated that total revenue, climate zones, yield, and variable cost were the variables most strongly associated with profitability across climate zones and system types. These findings suggest the potential value of regionally adapted and configuration-specific approaches. For example, enhancing revenue along with fish and plant yields may improve profitability in coupled aquaponics, whereas reducing TVC and TCP may be more effective in improving profitability in decoupled aquaponics. While the results suggest distinct pathways for assessing economic sustainability in coupled and decoupled aquaponics, this finding may reflect data imbalance, as only 9% of the dataset pertains to decoupled aquaponics. Hence, our findings are best viewed as hypothesis generating and in need of validation in future studies with larger and more representative datasets.

Across the system configurations, notable associations were observed between biophysical variables (e.g., hydroponic types, plant species, climates) and economic indicators such as total revenue, net returns, and yield. In addition, while input costs such as labor and energy costs were major inverse drivers of net returns and profitability in temperate climates, feed costs accounted for significant cost inputs in tropical climates.

To address the variability and data gaps in economic assessment, we developed APECO—a metadata-driven Excel-based calculator presented here as a prototype proof-of-concept framework. The tool integrates climate and system-specific parameters and allows for manual input of localized data, enhancing its adaptability. Over time, and with further data integration and validation, APECO has the potential to facilitate real-time decision-making by enabling users to simulate various investment and production scenarios, supporting robust prior

economic risk assessment. However, the tool is currently limited by the exclusion of capital costs, and it is yet to be field validated. Future improvements will integrate capital investment structures and further undergo real-world calibration to improve its reliability and practical relevance for stakeholders.

In conclusion, while aquaponic and hydroponic systems have huge potential in sustainable food production, in order to achieve an increased adoption, profitability would have to be consistent based on system configuration informed by local constraints, biological efficiencies, and market dynamics. Once validated, tools like APECO could be critical in translating complex data into actionable insights, potentially contributing to the development of more economically and environmentally sustainable food production systems.

Author Contributions

Ewumi Azeez Folorunso: conceptualization, software, investigation, methodology, formal analysis, data curation, writing – original draft. **Radek Gebauer:** investigation, methodology, formal analysis, software, data curation, investigation, writing – original draft. **Jan Mraz:** conceptualization, validation, funding acquisition, visualization, writing – review and editing.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Figure S1:** Barplot showing the percentage distribution of the crop species of studies on the economic viabilities of soilless systems ($n = 145$). Lettuce was the most commonly studied crop in economic viability studies, representing over 30% of all observations, followed by tomato. **Figure S2:** Percentage distribution of fish species used in economic viability studies on aquaponics systems ($n = 145$). Tilapia was the most frequently studied species, representing nearly half (49%) of all observations, followed by African catfish and various polyculture combinations. The dominance of Tilapia reflects its high adaptability, fast growth rate, and established market demand in aquaponic systems across various climate zones. **Figure S3:** The percentage distribution of the hydroponic types commonly used in the studies in economic viabilities of soilless systems ($n = 145$). Floating raft system (44%) was the most used in the studies. The studies that did not mention the hydroponic system type were indicated with Na (not available). **Figure S4:** Grouped barplot comparing the mean fish yield (kg/m³) between coupled and decoupled aquaponic systems for commonly reared species (Tilapia and African catfish) in aquaponic systems. Bars represent mean yield per species, grouped by aquaponic system type. **Figure S5:** Boxplot showing the benefit–cost ratio (BCR) across different types of hydroponic systems ($n = 34$). System types with fewer than two observations were not included in the analysis. **Figure S6:** Boxplot showing the comparisons of benefit–cost ratio (BCR) between aquaponics and hydroponics ($n = 34$). System types with fewer than two observations were not included in the analysis. **Figure S7:** Boxplots showing plant yield (comprising lettuce and tomato) (kg/m²/year) across (A) soilless system types and (B) hydroponic system configurations. Outliers were removed using the interquartile range (IQR) method. Variability in yield is evident across different production systems, including single and combined hydroponic technologies (e.g., NFT, FRS, and hybrids). **Figure S8:** Boxplots showing payback period across various hydroponic types in aquaponic systems. “NFT” indicates Nutrient film technique; “FRS” indicates floating raft system; and “multiple” indicates a combination of more than two hydroponic types. The boxes represent interquartile range with median values, with the whiskers indicating variability outside the upper and lower quartiles. The dash lines indicate insufficient data. Sample sizes are $n = 32$. The dashed lines indicate insufficient data. **Figure S9:** Boxplot showing labor cost as a percentage of total variable cost across different hydroponic types in soilless system operations. Data represent cleaned values with extreme outliers removed using the IQR method. **Figure S10:** Boxplot showing electricity cost as a percentage of total variable cost across different climate zones in soilless system operations. Data represent cleaned values with extreme outliers removed using the IQR method. Climate zones are classified according to the Köppen system, and the analysis highlights variability in energy dependence among regions, likely influenced by temperature regulation demands. **Figure S11:** Pearson correlation heat map showing pairwise relationships among key economic and technical variables in aquaponic systems. The intensity of the color denotes

the strength and direction of the correlation, while the embedded values indicate correlation coefficients annotated with significance levels ($*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$). The heat map reveals both cost and yield dynamics that underpin net returns in different configurations. **Figure S12:** A cosine similarity heat map showing the interrelations between the variables in hydroponics ($n = 16$). The closer the cosine value is to 1, the stronger the directional alignment between the two variables. The hydroponic panels do not include fish species. TCP and total VC, indicates total capital cost and total variable cost, respectively.

Biographies

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